

FUNDAMENTALS OF THE FORMATION OF A CULTURE OF COMMUNICATION OF TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM.

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Annotation: This article highlights the issues of the formation of a culture of treatment based on pedagogical communication of teachers in education system.

Keywords: pedagogical communication, culture of communication, education, pedagogical requirements, pedagogical activity.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'lim tizimida o'qituvchilarning pedagogik muloqoti asosida muomala madaniyatini shakllantirish masalalari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik muloqot, muomala madaniyati, ta'lim-tarbiya, pedagogik talab, pedagogik faoliyat.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещаются вопросы формирования культуры обращения на основе педагогического общения педагогов в системе образования.

Ключевые слова: педагогическое общение, культура общения, воспитание, педагогические требования, педагогическая деятельность.

Currently, the state policy in the field of personnel training presupposes the intellectual and spiritual and moral education of a person, the achievement of his manifestation as a comprehensively developed personality. The culture of communication and communication of a teacher plays an important role in the implementation of this social requirement, in obtaining knowledge, forming creative abilities, and intellectual development of every citizen. Therefore, it is worth noting that the demand and responsibility for the teaching profession have also increased, and their responsibilities to society have increased even more.

Teachers are responsible for such great tasks as the revival and further enhancement of our great spirituality, the improvement of the national education system, strengthening its national foundation, harmonization with the requirements of the time, bringing it to the level of world standards, the formation of students' skills of independent and free thinking. The fulfillment of these tasks is achieved due to the culture of interaction between the teacher and the students, who is the main conductor of reforms in the field of education. The formation of the student's spiritual atmosphere is manifested through the example of the teacher's high morality. In this place, the personal and social behavior of the teacher is formed and improved on the basis of the culture of pedagogical communication. In pedagogical communication, the best qualities and actions of the teacher are manifested as the ideal of the student. The perfect organization of the holistic pedagogical process also does not give positive results if the student's views on the teacher's personality, his behavior, pedagogical skills do not

correspond to his spiritual culture. Rigid authoritarian discipline between the teacher's subject and the student's object also negatively affects the culture of interaction, as a result of which the inner feeling of the student, as well as his personal qualities, does not develop. The culture of pedagogical communication is the most important tool guiding the activity of a teacher to success, the most important quality of a teacher in this is his attitude based on the culture of communication. Conversion has its own definition in all philosophical and psychological sciences. Appeal as a category of pedagogy is the pedagogical ability of a teacher aimed at finding a way to the hearts of students, winning their love, approaching them, from a pedagogical point of view, interacting with students in the educational process.

Based on the teacher's entry into communication with students:

1. Demonstrates his creativity and pedagogical skills.
2. Educates the younger generation in the spirit of our national ideology and national culture.
3. He forms a harmonious personality based on our eastern custom and traditions.
4. Demonstrating their educational potential, each student will find their way to the heart. The appeal is an important component of the teacher's activity, embodying a huge pedagogical potential.

In the pedagogical address, the teacher must strictly adhere to the following activities:

- the formation of the teacher's parenting skills. Be able to select words and tone related to the educational process and influence it;
- be able to use speech, pauses, movements, gestures that attract the attention of the student who is the object of communication, to be aware of the educational impact;
- to involve the student in communication, knowing his inner psyche, the characteristics of the psychologist, to involve students in educational communication before the lesson preparation;
- students' knowledge of educational ways of verbal interaction. The teacher's speech should be fluent, positively influence the student's consciousness.

Finally, the teacher's daily communication with students leads to the fact that he notices a deep meaning and real reasons in the behavior of students in various situations, for which he himself often uses recorded facts and behavioral techniques of students as an example. The teacher's relationship with students is considered as a means of managing education, acting both unifying and interchangeable. Communication takes place within the framework of relationships. The appeal, which is a means of management, precedes pedagogical activity. Pedagogical communication acts as a process of mutual exchange of information in the pedagogical activity of a teacher. In the process of communicating with pupils, the teacher directly receives an unusually diverse information about his pupils, about the student collective as a whole, about various internal phenomena occurring in it, determines further educational plans, pedagogical activity.

As a result of the teacher's achievement of a culture of interaction with pupils, the following situations arise:

- through pedagogical communication, the teacher creates a specific environment of communication with the ward object. In such an environment, the teacher demonstrates his system of abilities, such as psychological, mimic, pantomime, oratory, affectation;
- the teacher's mercy, open face, sincere attitude is the key to achieving positive results in communication;

-the teacher's constant reliance on psychological knowledge when communicating with a team of pupils maintains the same balance in educational activities;

- as a teacher interacts with a group of students, with good treatment, he will be able to understand even the most subtle layers hidden in his emotions.

The method of formation by the teacher of individual styles of culture of communication with pupils includes the following stages:

1. The study of individual and personal characteristics of the communication culture of students is carried out on the basis of an independent analysis of the personal characteristics of students, comprehensive characteristics, the correct organization of communication by the teacher.

2. Identification of shortcomings arising in personal communication and search for immediate measures to eliminate them: overcoming rudeness, neglect and other negative situations in communication.

3. The teacher should develop for himself the methods of communication culture that are convenient for him, and compare achievements and shortcomings with self-observation.

4. Effective use of aspects inherent in our national tradition and spirituality, corresponding to the styles of communication culture.

5. Not to deviate from the laws of pedagogical activity in the culture of communication, consolidating this style (in the process of pedagogical practice and professional development).

Young teachers who are just beginning their pedagogical activity need to systematically work on the formation of a culture of communication with students in order to improve their professional skills. The culture of pedagogical communication in the organization of the educational process is a force that directs the direct interaction of teachers and pupils to achieve a certain goal in unity.

At the same time, it should be emphasized that the teacher should take into account the following situations:

- the teacher's observance of the culture of communication from the very beginning of educational activities, during which he plans daily communication with the teacher and the student team in accordance with the situation, paying attention to each action, the tone of the word, mastering the best features of traditional communication;

-note various situations in the collective of the class on the basis of communication, to evaluate the behavior of students, comparing it with the previous state, with the state after learning activities;

- continuously eliminate shortcomings by critically analyzing the results of your own communication style. Formation of the necessary word, pleasant tone of voice, manner of behavior;

-for the effective existence of a culture of pedagogical communication, it is not enough to know its prerequisites, the beginning of interaction with pupils characteristic of the "teacher - student" tradition and attracting the attention of the object of communication to solving important tasks on the basis of mutual exchange of opinions;

-for the effective functioning of a culture of communication, it is necessary, that is, what should be understood by attracting the reader's attention? This means that the teacher, demonstrating his politeness, culture, excellent behavior, the ability to find a way in the hearts of students in communication, takes as a basis the socio-psychological basis of organizational forms of communication culture.

The pedagogical impact on the basis of these situations is subject to special requirements for the culture of pedagogical communication of the teacher, ethics and etiquette, benevolence, etiquette of behavior. These qualities are the key to the success of the teacher in the class team, in the ability to communicate with parents, organize and direct educational activities with students for a specific purpose.

A young teacher who adheres to the culture of pedagogical communication, which is a unique quality of professional activity, should combine the following features:

- a socially and politically active person with a high level of spirituality corresponding to the socio-political needs and needs of our country, strong and stable beliefs, commitment to the national idea and ideology of independence, patriotism, a sense of self-sacrifice;
- formation of skills and competence in sincere attachment to pupils, understanding of motives, behavior of any of their needs, interests, actions;
- pedagogical observation in relation to events taking place in society, taking place in the world, in relation to nature, being, interpersonal, intergroup, interethnic relations, the ability to strive for novelty, creative search;
- accessibility- rational understanding of the peculiarities of behavior, relationships of people in all spheres of pedagogical activity, reflexive attitude to their activities;
- factorial and rational attitude to any emergency situations, innovations occurring in society, as well as to socio-economic changes, the ability to set the right goals, make plans, exercise direct control; be able to do, manage and show their potential;
- show organizational and managerial abilities in teaching activities, mass actions in temporary group relations in the socio-typical system;
- breadth of outlook and thinking, fecundity of interest in the knowledge of secular knowledge, a penchant for scientific research, a systematic increase in the level of a certain scientific potential and pedagogical skills;
- competence in communicating with pupils, logical conciseness of speech culture, meaningfulness, possession of affective power, armed with psychological influence. For every teacher, it is professionally necessary to be able to correctly convey factor information to students and convince the interlocutor of it. At the same time, the teacher's communication culture and the breadth of his spiritual world are important.

The pedagogical activity of a teacher is continuous, therefore, in the systematic formation of a culture of communication, he should pay attention to the following areas:

1. Self-awareness from the point of view of high pedagogical activity (knowledge of one's qualities, positive and weak sides in communication regarding mutual exchange of opinions) and self-education on this basis through mutual exchange of opinions.
2. Develops communicative abilities in interaction with people, trains correct predictive feelings based on communication, analyzes his ideal ideas about communication, reflexive ideas about how others evaluate their capabilities (teaching staff, students, parents).
3. Work on the basis of specialized exercises for the development of important features of etiquette behavior.
4. To carry out various social work with students and parents aimed at educational goals, while improving pedagogical organizational skills on the basis of mutual understanding.
5. To form skills of overcoming negative situations that arise in the process of communication, to create a system of situations that develop assertiveness and tact.

Even if a teacher carries out activities based on a culture of communication, it is quite natural that various misunderstandings and conflicts arise between the student body. In the process of pedagogical communication of any experienced teacher, specific difficulties arise. The teacher is responsible for any pedagogical situation occurring in the classroom. This is a typical phenomenon that manifests itself in the pedagogical activity of all periods. Especially this situation generates problematic situations in the pedagogical activity of young teachers who are just starting their activities. Constant monitoring of the educational activities of young teachers with students, their correct direction, should be entrusted to the pedagogical community of all educational institutions, teachers-mentors.

Communicative competencies:

- the use of various forms and methods in communicating with students, parents, the management of an educational institution, colleagues;
- establishment of practical, business or personal relationships with all participants of pedagogical practice;
- search for effective ways and means of communicating information to students;
- ability to listen to the answer or personal opinion of the student on assignments. to know;
- to prevent, eliminate or develop conflicts arising in pedagogical processes;
- strengthening the relationship between the team and students at different stages of learning;
- creating a healthy competitive environment in the team;
- stimulating students' activities;
- responding to a mistake in the student's reaction or shortcomings in his behavior;
- achieving educational cooperation with students.

The teacher should rely, first of all, on his talents, pedagogical skills in order to quickly cope with various conflict situations that may arise in the process of communicating with pupils. The achievements that are achieved on the basis of pedagogical communication are the product of the creative work of the teacher. Undoubtedly, this work will have its pros and cons. It is enough only to rationally assess each situation, plan it correctly, and organize rational communication in educational processes.

It should be noted that the realization of the educational potential of the culture of communication is largely determined by the personal qualities of the teacher. *Properly selected in all respects, the style of culture of pedagogical communication, corresponding to the spiritual level, the unique characteristics of the teacher, contributes to the solution of a set of the following tasks:*

first, the special attention and passion of each student in communication, simplifies the overall process of communication with the class team, prepares the ground for the free pedagogical activity of the teacher, easily resolves conflict situations;

secondly, the organization of interaction with each student on the basis of free communication, the choice of acceptable pedagogical and psychological communication styles in accordance with his age characteristics opens the way to the knowledge of his psyche, "penetration" into his inner world;

thirdly, in pedagogical communication, the spiritual and moral norms of the teacher are the key to success, increase efficiency education, help the educator at all stages provides calm feelings of satisfaction with their activities.

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